

Factors Affecting the Implementation of Competency-Based Curriculum in Lower Secondary Schools In Uganda: A Systematic Literature Review

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Abstract: This systematic review aimed to identify and synthesize the factors affecting the implementation of competency-based curricula (CBC) in secondary schools in Uganda. The review of the Scopus database followed a comprehensive search strategy, including electronic databases and gray literature searches conducted to identify relevant studies published between 2013 and 2022. 27 studies were included in the review because of their relatedness to the study, and data were extracted and synthesized using a thematic synthesis approach. Based on PRISMA as a method secondary data were used in the study. The study identified challenges affecting the implementation of Competency Based curriculum; teachers did not receive training about this curriculum, textbooks for the new curriculum were inadequate hence affecting the implementation of competency-based curriculum.

The findings indicate that teacher-student ratios were too high, 1:70 in one classroom hence affecting the implementation.

The review found that several factors influenced the implementation of CBC, including teacher training and professional development, the availability of resources, stakeholder support, and alignment with national policies and priorities. Challenges such as inadequate funding, a lack of stakeholders' involvement, inadequate monitoring and supervision, a lack of infrastructure, and resistance to change were identified. The review also identified the importance of effective leadership, teacher motivation, and student-centered learning in facilitating successful implementation. The review highlights the need for continued efforts to support CBC implementation in Uganda, particularly through targeted training and support for teachers and stakeholders, and increased investment in resources and infrastructure. According to the results, it recommended for all secondary schools and the government ensure that instructional materials are available at the school premises, proper training of personnel to ensure effective implementation of educational policy, and the involvement of all stakeholders and their roles and responsibilities should be spelled out clearly

Keywords: Lower secondary school curriculum, Competency-based curriculum, curriculum implementation, Uganda.

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Introduction

The world around us is changing and we must prepare our children to face new challenges in the 21st Century. They need to acquire new skills and knowledge of the latest technologies and this requires serious curriculum reform to fit the current demand in the world market and life skills for proper and sustaining economy. The school curriculum must reflect these changes, and thus, prepares our children for the challenges (Hassan & Shkak, 2020). Competency-based education is a system that focuses on the development of practical skills and knowledge that are required for students to succeed in the workplace (UNESCO, 2022).

The education system should be able to provide skills, knowledge, and ability for an individual to have the potential and values to work in and provide the necessary service needed in the field of work (Nakabugo et al., 2011). Although the origin of competence-based education has been traced differently by different authors, literature shows that most of them concur with the point that CBE has most directly descended from the behavioral objective movement of the late 1950s and early 1960s. Despite objections against the original behaviouristic competency-based education approach, the innovation has now made a comeback and is more alive than ever. Competence-based education programs are now popular in both the developed world for example United Kingdom, France, Germany, and Netherlands, and the developing world such as South Africa, Tanzania, Mozambique, and Ethiopia. The emphasis on competence-based education is due to the growing recognition of the need for direct development of capabilities and not just at acquiring qualifications, as capabilities are perceived as a prerequisite for employability and also a link between education and the labor market (Mulder et al., 2011).

The 1989 United Nations Convention on the Rights of Child (CRC, 1989), linked life skills to education by stating that education should be directed towards the development of the child's fullest potential. The 1990 Jomtien Declaration on Education For All (EFA) cites life skills as essential learning tools for survival, capacity development, and quality of life. This was reinforced by the 2000 Dakar World Forum which stated that all young people and adults have the right to benefit from education that includes learning to know, to do, and to live together this means that implementation of life skills is critical to the attainment of the EFA goal. (D'Sa, 1993)

Scotland, Finland, and Canada implemented CBC and it was successful because of the vigorous training of teachers and good financial support given to the education sector by those governments and because they prioritize the education of children with the greatest percentage given to the education sector to support the implementation of CBC. It was successful in Rwanda because her neighbors had good curricula, as well as teachers and complex research, done by the Ministry of Education and the national curriculum of Rwanda. For South Africa, the curriculum failed in the implementation stages because of the attitude, development, and competence of the teachers (Ngeno et al., 2021).

1.1. Lower secondary competency-based curriculum

The curriculum is how countries around the world equip the public with the values, knowledge, skills, and attitudes necessary for their economic and social participation in achieving national and individual development (Wambua, (2019). It refers to any kind of learning designed and led by schools, whether it takes place in an individual setting or group, and whether it takes place outside or inside the school (Kelly, 2013). Knowledge-based approach to learner-centered/skills-based approach (Baguma, 2020). Martin and Griffiths (2014) note that this change was necessary to ensure that learners could easily understand the concepts taught in this approach without undue stress during the learning process. Competency-based instruction focuses on what learners are expected to do rather than what they are expected to know (Makunja, 2016). In theory, such a program is learner-centered and capable of adapting to the changing needs

of students, teachers, and society. Curriculum is often considered a set of experiences that learners have during their learning process logically, allowing them to understand concepts easily and without much stress. The advancement of educational programs is a continuous process driven by the need to respond to change, as Stabback (2016) points out. A quality educational program must align with global trends in information developments, media advances and changing job market needs to ensure that students have the skills needed to succeed. There is currently a global shift towards competency-based education, which, as Gardner (2017) identifies, has its roots in the 1920s, when educational reforms were linked to action plans that outlined produce desired results (Williamson, 2000).

The Uganda Vision 2040 aims to transform Uganda into a modern and prosperous country, while the National Development Plan recognizes the existing weaknesses in education, including the low efficiency and variable quality at the secondary level. Sustainable Development Goal 4 advocates for inclusive and quality education, while the National Development Plan II focuses on the enhancement of human capital, development, strengthening mechanisms for quality, effective efficient service delivery, and improvement of quality and relevance of skills development. The NRM Manifesto (2016-2021), emphasizes continuous assessment examination systems, strengthening soft skills, which promote self-esteem, conscientiousness, and a generally positive attitude to work, and promoting e-learning and computer literacy to enhance learning outcomes. All these are lacking and where they exist it is at a minimum level.

In alignment with the above, the Education and Sports Sector Strategic Plan (2017/20) advocates for the delivery of equitable, relevant, and quality education for all. The current secondary school curriculum of Uganda, although highly regarded by some, is focused on the needs of a tiny academically oriented elite yet the needs of the majority of learners need to be the focus. The Ministry of Education and Sports (MoES) through the National Curriculum Development Centre therefore, undertook a review of the Lower Secondary Curriculum, aimed at providing a learning environment, opportunities, interactions, tasks, and instructions that foster deep learning by putting the learner at the Centre of the learning experience.

However, Uganda's lower secondary school curriculum and the mode of secondary school teaching has been knowledge-based, content-centered, and examination-oriented, as opposed to competency-based entailing the acquisition of skills, values, and attitudes. "Youth need to access quality, productive, and relevant education above basis of schooling, and which bridges the life skills, technical training, and non-formal education" (UNICEF Report, 2019).

In Uganda, the government has implemented a competency-based curriculum for secondary schools to improve the quality of education and prepare students for the job market. However, the implementation of this curriculum has faced several challenges. This systematic review aims to identify the factors affecting the implementation of competency-based curricula in lower secondary schools in Uganda.

1.2 Aims of the Review

To investigate the factors affecting the implementation of the competency-based curriculum in lower secondary schools in Uganda.

Specifically, the following research questions were addressed:

1. How is a competency-based curriculum being implemented in secondary schools in Uganda?
2. What are the factors affecting the implementation of competency-based curriculum in secondary schools?
3. What are the urgently needed government and international efforts to support and improve the implementation of CBC in Uganda?

1.3 Implementation of a competency-based curriculum (problem statement)

With the shift from the knowledge-based or content-based to the thematic or competency-based curriculum in Uganda since 2020 February, many complaints have been realized from the parents, students, teachers, the entire community,

and other stakeholders in the education sector in Uganda about the new lower secondary school curriculum. All the public school teachers more so those in the rural areas are the ones complaining a lot about how to use instructional materials due to insufficient training received by teachers. Private schools are also expressing the same problem and they are despising the new curriculum but it is unclear what is happening in those schools. It needs to be investigated so that clear information can be submitted to the Ministry of Education and Sports as well as the National Curriculum Development Centre.

Research Methodology

The research method chosen to conduct this research was the systematic literature review (S.I.R), following the guidelines posed by (Katrine Nesje, 2021) systematic review is based on qualitative research where data were analyzed from secondary data.

This study is grounded on already published articles, publications, and my personal experiences in line with the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) that were used to guide the systematic review process (Creswell, 2018). A comprehensive search was conducted in an electronic database, Scopus using relevant keywords such as competency-based curriculum, secondary schools, implementation, and Uganda.

2.1 Search Strategy

The research used terms of competency-based curriculum to reach a wider range of studies. After checking preliminary hits, three key terms including competency-based curriculum, and factors affecting implementation, it should be noted that some studies carried out before 2013 were excluded as they did not provide relevant information regarding the new change. The search was run from 2013 to 2022, English language was also used as a criterion to select articles related to the review (B., 2015). Key terms were searched on the Scopus database by title and abstract. When built-in filters were available, the search only included peer-reviewed journal articles written in English in the fields of education, psychology, and social sciences. After removing duplicates, all articles were screened by reading titles and abstracts to check if the studies were related to the research questions, non-related articles were excluded, and a list of included articles was formed.

2.2 Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria.

Eligibility criteria are based on the Prisma, study design, and date. Exclusion criteria mostly are unrelated, duplicated, unavailable full texts, or abstract-only papers. During the articles screening process, studies were included if they met all of the following inclusion criteria. Based on Scopus handwritten ideas were generated based on the following criteria, contained in the abstracts and published papers and books.

1. The implementation of competency-based curricula mainly in secondary schools.
2. The factors affecting the implementation of a competency-based curriculum with a focus on teacher professional development, attitudes of teachers toward this curriculum, working conditions of workers, monitoring, and evaluation.
3. The strategies that can be incorporated to solve the implementation challenges in Uganda are through the government and international corporations.
4. The study presented non-empirical data.
5. The study included papers published after 2013 about secondary schools on competency-based curriculum
6. The articles were published in the English language.

2.3 Data screening and extraction

As summarized in Fig 1, The initial search resulted in 131 published articles in the Scopus database searched using the keywords competency-based curriculum, implementation, and secondary schools in addition, no duplicates were realized since all the 131 articles are from one database (Glenn A, 2009). I used only the Scopus database to search for the articles and books related to this study. After the first screening which was by document type, only 104 articles and books were left for further screening, out of 104 articles, 18 articles were excluded because they were not written in English, and 86 articles and books remained after screening using language type. The second time, 86 articles were screened by abstracts and titles, 86 were screened by year of publication which was from 2013-2022, and 66 articles were left after removing other articles published before 2013. After applying the inclusion criteria to screen information from the title and abstract of the publications, 66 studies were left for data extraction review. 66 articles were reviewed by full text to assess their eligibility for this study but only 34 articles and books were eligible and the 34 were finally assessed to check on their relevancy to this study, 7 articles were excluded because they are relevant to the study being carried out. After the data extraction process, 7 studies were found to be unsuitable for the current study's aim. Finally, 27 qualified studies were retained and analyzed for the study. It is indicated in the figure below how the screening was done to come out with the final articles.

After the selection, all the included studies were read thoroughly and recorded using a data extraction form. The data extraction form was constructed by the authors and included the following sections: study title, author name, year of publication, the aim of the study, research questions, country or region, key terminology, implementation, and competency-based curriculum.

2.4 Study Relevance Assessment.

The researcher assessed the 34 articles in terms of their applicability and relevance to this systematic review and based on the current aims of the review. The researcher considered the "weight of evidence", which was referred to as a framework for the appraisal of the quality and relevance of evidence 7 articles were excluded for not being related to research questions, limited information in the seven papers which did not meet the inclusion criteria. Only 27 papers were coded to be the best and were used in this review.

Figure 2.1. Literature search and selection of articles for review

2.5 Data synthesis and analysis

An extensive systematic review of articles provided background information that helped the researcher collect the appropriate data about the aims of the study and the research questions (Burns et al., 2016). The researcher extensively reviewed the study on each question and category and synthesized the results across the studies. The main aim of this study was to explore the factors affecting the implementation of a competency-based curriculum. Data was analyzed on Scopus data and the results are as follows;

Most of the articles screened and included in this study are from social sciences with the highest percentage of 61.1% and others from different disciplines as indicated in the pie chart below. The competency-based curriculum is a cross-cutting curriculum that should be looked at from all disciplines this is why we used other subject areas to give us broad ground and knowledge in the struggle to implement this curriculum (Glenn A, 2009).

Figure 2.2 A pie chart shows articles used in this study on different disciplines

Figure 2.3. A graph represents the years of publication of articles used in this study

Current ideas about competency-based curricula given by different scholars were used to collect the information given

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Documents by type

Figure 2.4. A pie chart below shows the type of documents used in this study

The researcher decided to use published articles and books to conduct this study, the books and articles are closely related to the study objectives and aims. The analysis indicates that more articles are being published to improve the implementation of CBC evidenced by 92.6% as indicated in the pie chart above

Documents by affiliation

Compare the document counts for up to 15 affiliations.

Figure 2.5. A bar graph showing the number of articles published by different institutions

The institutions have taken part in providing papers on competency-based curriculum and this is reflected in the graph above. The top with many published articles on this curriculum and they have tried their best on how we can implement the competency-based curriculum in secondary schools and higher institutions of learning.

Findings and Discussions

The researcher came up with the following findings which fall under three categories: 1-Implementation of the competency-based curriculum in Uganda. 2-factors affecting the implementation of competency-based in secondary schools and possible strategies that can be incorporated to help Uganda implement the competency-based curriculum.

3.1 Implementation of Competency-based Curriculum in Uganda

In Uganda's case, the Competency-Based Curriculum was incorporated initially into the thematic curriculum, which was implemented in 2007 for primary one and the subsequent year lower primary from primary one to primary three. A thematic Curriculum is a curriculum in which the content is organized around common themes for the learners (Nakabugo et al., 2011). The thematic curriculum was designed with the following concepts in mind: the use of themes rather than departmentalized subjects; the use of mother tongue or local language as a medium of instruction; the class teacher system; the use of free and low-cost instructional materials; and continuous assessment.

3.1.1 Subject

We found out that Learners have to study a core of compulsory subjects and will be able to choose from a range of elective subjects that will allow them to follow their interests and specialize in a particular area (NCDC, 2020). The compulsory subjects at S1 & 2 are; English, Entrepreneurship, Mathematics, Biology, Chemistry, Physics (or General Science for learners with special educational needs), Geography, History, Kiswahili, Physical education, ICT, Religious Education, and Agriculture. At S3&4 there is a greater focus on a narrower range, with 7 compulsory subjects which are: Mathematics, English, Chemistry, Biology, Physics, (General Science), Geography, and History & Political Education, and a maximum of three elective subjects. At S3 and S4, emphasis should be placed on integrating ICT in all subjects so that learners fit the learner graduate profile at the end of the cycle.

The Lower Secondary Curriculum Menu consists of 21 subjects. A school is expected to select 15 subjects to be offered out of the 21 subjects on the menu. At S1&2, learners are expected to offer 13 compulsory subjects plus two electives. At S3&4 learners are expected to offer a minimum of 8 and a maximum of 10 subjects, out of which 7 are compulsory (NCDC, 2020).

3.1.2 Time allocations

The school Day starts at 8 am and instruction time will end at 2.40 pm. Between 2:40 pm and 4:30 pm, learners will have free time for their creativity and innovation. Learning time needs to be allocated at the school level so that periods are available for meaningful study in each of the Subjects. For example, some practical subjects will need longer periods than more theoretical ones. An Entrepreneurship project could well take a whole morning or afternoon. It is up to schools to decide how best to structure the learning periods for the Subjects to maximize the learning opportunities.

3.1.3 Teaching and Learning

The thrust of the new syllabuses is experiential and toward deeper understanding. This will require a shift from a 'knowledge transmission' mode to a more 'active-learning' approach in which learners are challenged to think for themselves, conclude solve problems, and make their judgments. Learners will need to take some control of their n learning, by sharing the use of appropriately-designed textbooks and accessing multimedia content where available. The reformed curriculum encourages schools to provide learners with increased opportunities to build work-related knowledge, experience, and skills. The generic skills have been integrated throughout the curriculum and can only be acquired through active approaches.

3.1.4 Assessment

The reformed, outcomes-based, curriculum requires a revised, skill-oriented approach to assessment that will support learning and reward achievement at all levels. This will be criterion-referenced to ensure that standards can be maintained year by year. The new curriculum emphasizes the assessment of the skills required for the world of work. The previous UCE "O" level examination is being revisited to include classroom-based assessment. Learners will still be formally assessed at the end of Senior 4, but the results of those assessments will lead to the award of a Uganda Certificate of Education (UCE) that will consist of learner's achievement for both formative and summative assessment (NCDC, 2020).

3.2 Factors affecting the effective implementation of the competency-based curriculum in the lower secondary schools in Uganda.

Below are the factors affecting the implementation of competency-based as recorded by this study:

3.2.1 Teacher's Professional Development

Teacher's professional development refers to activities that develop an individual's skills, knowledge, expertise, and other characteristics as a teacher. Professional development is generally defined locally in the teacher's questionnaires (IBE-UNESCO, 2017). Teachers' professional learning is of increasing interest as a critical way to support the increasingly complex skills and students' needs to learn to fit in the 21st century. Sophisticated forms of teaching are needed to develop students' competencies such as deep mastery of challenging content, critical thinking, complex problem solving, effective communication and collaboration, and self-direction. Curriculum implementation involves the daily classroom activities that the teacher is involved in, which monitor students' progress and evaluate the performance of the students. Teachers are responsible for implementing the newly introduced curriculum and deciding if it is having the desired effect on students learning to perform the assigned tasks teachers rely upon the curriculum materials, the teaching methodology, content knowledge of the curriculum, and their experiences (Wabule, 2021).

Teachers are very influential in curriculum reforms and without teachers' educational reforms may not be possible they are considered a major determinant and most important input to basic education and students' achievement as guides. For any educational reforms to be successful, teachers should be put into positive consideration right from the initial stage because it is practiced and implemented by them. The degree of a teacher's mastery of subject matter competence is vital and determines pupils' level of learning. Thus, it is not only the qualifications obtained by a teacher that could contribute to a teacher's quality but actual achievement in terms of subject matter competencies. Therefore, researchers attribute the low achievement of pupils in schools to teachers' inadequacy in understanding the subject matter (Muthanje et al., 2020). Therefore, it can be argued that professional development program encourages teachers to involve students in learning activities which enable both teachers and students to share their expertise and experience more systematically. It is upon this background that the government of Uganda came up with a continuous professional development program to update teachers' skills, attitudes, and approaches (Kani Olema et al., 2021).

Nombo (2022) pointed out that teacher training should be efficient such that teachers can be able to promote life skills and learning competence in students. However, this study found out that most teachers in Tanzania are not able to do it or in other words, they are inefficient in meeting the demands of the curriculum. It is unclear whether these teachers received good training in the teachers' colleges and it has been found out that teacher training programs are not to the expected level and need serious attention to improve the quality of teachers. In the case of Uganda, teachers seem not

to be trained in this lower secondary schools' curriculum, and without proper training, there is no effective and successful implementation and the quality of the quality of outputs.

The findings indicated that most of the teachers lacked sufficient knowledge and skills on this new reform and most could not use the instructional materials and the pedagogy and it was calculated that 86% of them were not able to facilitate the lessons. Most of the teachers failed to prepare relevant schemes

of work and lesson plans as reviewed during an inspection by the education officers and the head teacher. It was concluded by the researcher that the lesson plans and scheme of works did meet the standard of a competency-based curriculum because 78% of teachers could make lesson plans due to insufficient training. Further study indicated that the learner's participation in the classroom activities by the facilitators was very limited and less than 50% were able to carry out formative assessments. CBC was not implemented effectively in the sampled schools and recommended that regular training for in-service teachers should be conducted to enable them to acquire up-to-date teaching skills as required by the changes introduced in the curriculum. The teacher's responsibility under CBC is to design and prepare quizzes, assignments, instruments for experiments, books for reading, things for learners to observe, topics for debates, and projects to be accomplished under CBC. Therefore, the class must have adequate learning materials, an appropriate class size, an acceptable teaching load, and a teacher's competence.

3.2.2 Supervision and monitoring and implementation of CBC

The definition of supervision given by Samuel et al. (2021) is "leadership and attainment of specified goals," which encompasses goal-setting, professional development, instructional development, as well as the choice and revision of educational objectives through the use of teaching aids and institutional evaluation. The headteacher must make sure that the academic staff is clear about the school's educational goals and how they will be met.

According to Ribbins & ZHANG(2004), head teachers in Singapore are expected to provide instructional leadership to staff. According to Chinese headteachers, effective teaching is essential for student achievement and school reputation. Supervisory duties as collaborating closely with teachers to determine the needs and problems of students, fostering a positive group dynamic, and ensuring that teachers work effectively as a team. The principal is portrayed as a team builder who has complete control over the school's plans. Hence the requirement for head teachers to oversee syllabus coverage. The principal or headteacher, the deputy principal, and the assistant principal are responsible for monitoring instruction.

Chenge & Syomwene (2016) stated that the goal of supervision is to increase working effectiveness by encouraging teachers and students to pursue desirable teaching and learning behaviors to meet educational objectives. Therefore, instructional supervision is a fundamental part of the support that encourages teachers to be more effective and productive. As the quality and consistency of the information flow have a significant impact on the monitoring system's effectiveness, developing an effective feedback system is essential to the monitoring process. Therefore, a strong mechanism must be put in place to permit the free data flow, analytics, summaries, results, and other data that will serve as the foundation for the regular accessibility of big insights. Both an oral and a written format can be used to organize feedback.

School principals are in charge of making sure that the approved curriculum is implemented under the guidance of the teacher and is followed and met at various levels. The majority of principals are also in charge of assessing the competency and application of knowledge based on the curriculum of their teachers. The principal is also in charge of the classroom environment, which has a learning curve given that all of the infrastructure teachers and infrastructure students are under the principal's supervision.

3.2.3 Stakeholder's Attitude and Competency-Based Curriculum Implementation in Secondary Schools

On the perception of time and ICT, potential and prerequisites of effective integration of tablets secondary schools in rural Kenya. The combined method involved in the study was to conduct classroom observation, teacher interviews, student surveys, and focus groups. It was found that teachers always excluded students from the activities since they perceived learners to be slow during technology integration. Time designed or allocated for teaching specific content is not enough to cater to learners' experiences and academic challenges as per the interview conducted. The researchers recommended that teachers should be provided with more professional development to enable them to acquire pedagogical ability so that all learners are attended to. Makunja (2016) researched challenges facing teachers in implementing CBC in Morogoro Municipality, Tanzania. This study indicated clearly that education officers and curriculum developers experienced some challenges that impeded the execution of the CBC program in secondary schools. This study recommended a very important point that should be taken positively in most countries. In this world to have a successful implementation of any educational reform, teachers, parents, and other educational officers should be brought on board at the initial stage such that it is not new to them since they are the immediate stakeholders in curriculum formulation in schools. Teachers can work hard to achieve their set targets since teachers are put in the decision-making process. Failure to involve teachers in the decision-making process as far as any educational policy is concerned is planning to fail. The researcher found out that teachers of history were not using CBT approaches in the teaching and learning of the subject because they were not trained in CBT approaches. And because they were not trained it was the right time for them to revenge on the government by not using the approach. Instead, they used such traditional methods of assessment as class exercises tests, and examinations. These traditional methods often tested the ability to recall memorized facts, knowledge, and principles and were devoid of performance-based assessment (Kigwilu & Mokoro, 2022).

A study was conducted in Tanzania on teachers' attitudes toward the concept of CBC and training by Mwita et al.(2022). He found out that more than 30% of the respondents did not have the concept of competency-based education and training (CBET). He further explained that most of the teachers could not explain the terms and methodologies to be used in CBC. Most of them were still using the old learning approaches which are not in the newly formulated curriculum but students were committed and willing to participate actively in the implementation of CBC. It was important to notify them of the new curriculum and the implementation process. Secondary school teachers and parents who are focused need to be enthusiastic about applying the principles in practice and overcoming the barriers that are bound to emerge with CBC. A good perception of stakeholders towards any educational change is very important for successful implementation.

3.2.4 Working environments affecting the implementation of competency-based curriculum

The working environment plays a vital role in the performance of teachers and other stakeholders in schools. This involves working conditions, physical conditions, and psychological conditions. In most cases if the above factors are negative, teachers' performance is not always effective and efficient in teaching and learning). A conducive working environment provides comfort and security to teachers in carrying out their instructional work and other duties. It helps teachers to do their jobs and obligations well and wholeheartedly. Teachers with optimal performance can significantly impact the implementation of educational reforms

A study conducted by Irvine (2019), shows that the teachers are not well prepared for implementation of CBC from their teachers training colleges and universities. The researcher also revealed that some headteachers and district education officers and teachers to be trained and proper professional development given to them. The reality on the ground is that training is very important to implement CBC but there is not much funds and finance allocated for such activities by the government of funds to finance such programs remains an obstacle.

Kinyunyu (2020) noted that there is no positive correlation between the sizes of classrooms and the number of learners, and devices needed to assist in understanding some concepts in class. This indicates that a large number of students and limited space for class activities is a great hindrance to the effective implementation of CBC in secondary schools. This has made teaching as a profession to be complicated and tiresome. Classes have been divided into streams for the student to fit in those classrooms, teachers are having periods of too much division of classrooms into A, B, and C..... and teachers are supposed to teach in all those streams. It will be very interesting and interactive to have 45 students per class, teachers will not be stressed too much and this will promote effective teaching in schools.

Akomolafe & Adesua (2016) Conducted investigations on the impact of physical facilities on students and performance in academics in senior secondary schools in southwest Nigeria, kanyonga Chaudhary (2015) pointed out that various factors affect the implementation of the curriculum, such as teachers, learners, ideology and cultural learning in Tanzania. The research also pointed out that the government provided physical amenities such as sports fields, workshops, libraries, classrooms, laboratories, and sports. For the implementation of curriculum to be effective, the government should provide physical facilities such as libraries, classrooms, playing grounds and recreation centers, and devices for teaching and learning.

Kigwilu & Mokoro (2022) conducted a study on resource utilization toward the implementation of CBC in community colleges in Kenya. The investigation was carried out in colleges in Kenya on how the current physical amenities and resources of learning and teaching are used by Catholic-sponsored community colleges in Nairobi for appropriate Artisan and Craft Curriculum Implementation. They did not talk about library and textbooks which is the avenue for research work of students and the center for competency-based curriculum. It has also been noticed and confirmed by the researchers that schools were lacking playgrounds and yet this curriculum emphasizes co-curricular activities e.g., games and sports, and insufficient books for individual students.

3.2.5 Instructional materials and implementation of CBC

The lack of textbooks and instructional materials makes teaching challenging because students are unable to complete their oral or written assignments in class (Mohamed Isse Sidow, 2022). The 1994 KIE study found that the NFSs generally lacked resources and facilities that were appropriate and acceptable for teaching and learning. Learning materials were of poor quality and the physical facilities were generally inadequate and inappropriate. Textbooks and other teaching and learning resources are useful in putting the curriculum into practice. A lack of textbooks affects both teaching and learning. A curriculum designer must provide the support required for their advised programs to speed up implementation.

Waigera et al. (2020) conducted a study on the relationship between teachers' attitudes and the use of instructional materials in primary schools in Kenya. The finding of the study revealed that teachers with positive attitudes achieved a higher level of instructional content application unlike other teachers with negative attitudes could not accomplish the task using the designed teaching materials. The positivity of teachers puts a lot of interest in them and promotes good use of teaching material, and this helps them to deliver appropriate content so students can grasp it. Ngeno et al. (2021) point out the mindset of teachers was a critical element in encouraging the use of instructional techniques in ECDE practices. This study found that the positive attitude of a teacher was an essential characteristic of pre-primary school teaching. There was a need to cultivate positive attitudes toward using teaching materials during pre-service and in-service training sessions teachers were encouraged with their best practices in pre-primary school instruction and teaching. The mindset of the teacher relates significantly to the adoption of the competence-based curriculum, in that the more productive teachers are the most effective implementation of the competency-based curriculum.

Without appropriate resources like teacher's guide and learning materials anxiety and stress level of the teachers increases (Wanjiku, 2022). They are not able to implement the curriculum without materials that enhance the learning process in the classroom. In Uganda currently, they are using the old traditional textbooks in the implementation of a competency-based curriculum. It is not in line with this new curriculum and it is failing seriously because the demand of CBC is not the same as the one of a content-based curriculum. Parents may not accept buying those expensive devices needed to implement. Teachers who are not able to get access to the necessary materials feel completely ill-equipped and they do not have the motivation to implement the newly introduced curriculum.

3.3 Urgently needed government and international cooperation efforts to implement the competency-based curriculum in Uganda

Education reforms in this current situation need serious cooperation to have a successful implementation. There is a need to involve all the stakeholders fully engaged right from the start of curriculum design (Burns et al., 2016). This will help to avoid other scenarios like negative attitudes towards it by the teachers who are always left behind and some cases not fully engaged until the implementation stage. Different stakeholders are more likely to either; support or oppose the curriculum reform and they can influence the community in their lines of support or opposing

3.3.1 Individual and collective sense-making support the implementation

Sense-making in curriculum design and implementation involves the interpretation of curriculum policies, analyzing how teachers can implement curriculum, what to teach and exclude concerning CBC, and how important the curriculum may be to pupils. Furthermore, establishing the new knowledge and associated practices with the existing ones is key for teachers and other stakeholders is important. Sense-making can also influence educational achievement and attainment which is directly aligned with student engagement. Collective sense-making is based on shared values, and cultures and assesses the actions of key stakeholders.

Lack of coherent shared sense of making at the group level might expose the challenges or obstacles for curriculum reform. There should be a clear understanding of school headteachers and teachers in schools to avoid failure of the implementation in schools. Targeted communication can disseminate a lot of new approaches and guidelines to embrace new pedagogical practices with the former curriculum and identify the gaps. Involvement of many stakeholders more so educator staff within the Designed Based Implementation Research (DBIR). Leadership techniques and methods should emphasize participatory leadership styles and engagement (Gouédard et al., 2020). Leaders will be able to discuss, refine, and collectively get feedback about the new curriculum in comparison with the old curriculum.

3.3.2 Teachers' ownership of the new curriculum is essential to support change

Teachers need to be given ownership of curriculum reform as key implementers. Teachers are always influential to implementers and their ownership provides control feeling, support in terms of physical investments, and mental innovations.

The study is related to "ownership" in curriculum reform where teachers feel the curriculum is "theirs". This has enabled teachers to change their attitudes and the ownership is accompanied by the willingness to take positive responsibilities, risks, and confidence. Taking responsibility depends on the ability and authority of the teachers to speak and understand certain concepts in the curriculum. Their understanding of the students' needs and abilities, and how they use instructional materials that could reform successfully (UNESCO, 2012).

School leaders are very important in educational reforms more so curriculum implementation, they create the bridge between the school activities and the community. They can implement strategies that are suitable for the schools to adopt a policy depending on their existing cultures that facilitate teaching and learning. Uganda as a country should utilize the Parent Teachers Association, (PTA), and the board of governors in different schools such that they can execute the policy. School leaders can convince teachers to implement new curriculum or any educational reform in the school, more especially in schools where leaders are given the responsibility for curriculum and exercise instructional leadership (Gouédard et al., 2020).

3.3.3 A targeted communication strategy contributes to building global support

Providing quality information depends on effective communication through openness and a positive attitude toward educational reform. In the management of any organization, communication is a key element for its success since it reduces the uncertainty associated with curriculum reform. Before passing out a reform, teachers should be informed in advance such that preparation is made.

Teachers might not be sure of their roles and responsibilities, parents might not be aware of their responsibilities as far new curriculum is concerned, it is paramount that communication is made effective to avoid misconceptions about any educational reform.

3.3.4 Assessing the available resources dedicated to curriculum reform

The availability of funds and their sustainability is important because it determines the success and degree of implementation of the reform. Insufficient or lack of funding increases the teachers' workload and creates fear and uncertainty in them. In Scotland, teachers are the main impediments to curriculum implementation. Resources are the key influencer and it has got the long-term commitment of different stakeholders and the flow of curriculum vision and mission. Teachers always perceive that they are not important as far as educational reform is concerned and this makes them temporary support they may also consider the curriculum reform as temporary this calls for a transparent allocation of finance to support the whole curriculum right from the start with the effective engagement of teachers to support the curriculum (Gouédard et al., 2020)

Covid-19 has also raised the issue of equity in students accessing technology and it's not a simple task for a country like Uganda to provide platforms for online studies for all students. it was seen during the pandemic whereby only urban schools and private schools within the country accessed online studies. This goes to the Ministry of Education and Sports via the National Curriculum Development Centre that technology needs to first be integrated into education properly for the successful and easy implementation of CBC.

3.3.5 The selection and professional development of teachers are the key

Teachers need to receive continuous professional development since it equips teachers with the skills and knowledge needed for reforms. In Finland, curriculum reform is decentralized at the municipality level and schools establish their curriculum according to national curriculum guidelines. teachers are highly professional, qualified, and autonomous meaning that the selection of teachers is also very important and must be done on qualifications and proper professional development (Indicators, 2019). Singapore, Finland, Canada, China, and Australia countries having high-performing education systems, have well-developed policies that train and support teachers as professionals (Darling-Hammond et al., 2017). Teachers should have cognitive and socio-emotional skills and this can be useful in the classroom. The

teacher education program in Finland is extremely selective as they recruit from the top quartile of upper secondary graduates.

Recommendation

The findings of this systematic review suggest that the implementation of a competency-based curriculum in secondary schools in Uganda is affected by various factors, including teacher-related factors, and system-related factors. The success of the implementation largely depends on the availability of resources, adequate training for teachers, and effective policy implementation.

Teacher-related factors, including inadequate training, resistance to change, inadequate resources, and overcrowded classrooms, affect the ability of teachers to effectively deliver the curriculum. To address these issues, the government should provide adequate training for teachers, ensure that there are adequate resources, and reduce class sizes to improve the quality of education.

System-related factors, including inadequate funding, lack of policy implementation, and limited stakeholder involvement, affect the success of the implementation of the new curriculum. To address these issues, the government should provide adequate funding for the implementation of the new curriculum, ensure that policies and guidelines are effectively implemented, and involve stakeholders in the implementation process to ensure their support.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the implementation of competency-based curricula in secondary schools in Uganda is affected by various factors, including teacher-related factors, student-related factors, and system-related factors. The success of the implementation largely depends on the availability of resources, adequate training for teachers, and effective policy implementation. To address the challenges facing the implementation of the new curriculum, the government should provide adequate funding, ensure that policies and guidelines are effectively implemented, and involve stakeholders in the implementation process.

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